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Evidence of northern Turolian savanna-woodland from the Dorn-Dürkheim 1 fauna (Germany)

Loïc Costeur, Olivier Maridet, Sophie Montuire, Serge Legendre

Abstract Western European Turolian mammalian faunas and palaeoenvironments are less well known than middle and early late Miocene ones for which more data exist at a time when major climate events occurred (Middle Miocene Climatic Optimum followed by Late Middle Miocene Climatic Cooling). In this respect, rich faunas represent exceptional windows into mammalian diversity and biogeography. They constitute key points to understand local palaeoenvironments and refine larger-scale patterns. Dorn-Dürkheim 1 is one of the richest mammalian faunas of Western Europe with at least 79 species of mammals. We investigate this fauna and compare its composition to the faunal and biogeographic context of the European late Miocene. A community-based analysis of body masses of the constituent species together with an original approach on predator–prey biomasses are also attempted to reconstruct its

palaeoenvironment. While its composition reflects the known late Miocene context and fits in the biogeographic North–South pattern evidenced by earlier studies, the reconstructed landscape is different from previous hypotheses of densely forested habitats. Our results suggest the presence of a savanna-woodland biome more open than previously thought, in a subtropical-like and seasonal climate. Other palaeoecological studies on elements of the large mammal fauna confirm this interpretation.

Keywords late Miocene, Europe, Palaeoenvironments, Mammalian palaeocommunity, Body mass, Biomass

Introduction

The Turolian is biochronologically defined as the European Land Mammal Age covering the latest part of the late Miocene. Its beginning coincides with the European Mammal Zone MN11. By contrast with the previous Land Mammal Age (Vallesian), the Turolian in Europe is characterised by a drastic decrease in hominoid primate diversity (Spasov et al. 2012) and the disappearance or strong decrease of several taxa of early Miocene, or even earlier, origin (e.g. Spalacidae, Gliridae, Palaeomerycidae, Palaeochoeridae). It further sees the increase in abundance and dominance of specific families such as the Muridae or Bovidae (Bonis et al. 1992; Daams et al. 1988; Maridet and Costeur 2010). This faunal transition is usually interpreted as the result of a long-lasting evolution of the global climate towards cooler and more open terrestrial environments. Although a global phenomenon, this pattern still shows local to continental scale particularities that request rich locality-based fossil records to refine its understanding.

This article is a contribution to the special issue “Dorn-Dürkheim 1, Germany: A highly diverse Turolian fauna from mid-latitude Europe”

L. Costeur (corr. author)
Naturhistorisches Museum Basel, Augustinergasse 2,
4001 Basel, Switzerland
e-mail: Loic.Costeur@bs.ch

O. Maridet
Naturhistorisches Museum Wien, Burgring 7,
1010 Wien, Austria

S. Montuire
Laboratoire EPHE Paléobiodiversité et Evolution & UMR CNRS
6282 Biogéosciences, Université de Bourgogne, 6 Bd Gabriel,
21000 Dijon, France

S. Legendre
Laboratoire de Géologie de Lyon, UMR CNRS 5276, Université
Lyon 1 et Ecole Normale Supérieure de Lyon,
69622 Villeurbanne, France

These records are rather rare in the late Miocene of Europe or have never been analysed in depth.

Dorn-Dürkheim has long been known as one of the richest Western European faunas of the late Miocene. With at least 79 mammal species, it is indeed extraordinarily rich for an MN11 (Turolian) fauna. Most of its mammal species were dealt with in previous contributions (Bernor and Franzen 1997; Cerdeño 1997; Gaziry 1997; Gentry and Kaiser 2009; Franzen and Storch 1975; Kaiser et al. 2003, 2004; van der Made 1997; Morlo 1997; Roth and Morlo 1997; Storch 1978; Storch and Dahlmann 2000). Part of the other mammals, which are still to be described, some are gathered in this issue (Aiglstorfer and Costeur 2013; Azanza et al. 2013; Fahlke et al. 2013; Franzen 2013b; Pickford and Pourabrishami 2013). A number of questions arise when one investigates such a rich fauna: how is the huge diversity taxonomically distributed? Is there dominance or an even distribution of the constituent families? How does it compare to other Turolian localities? Is there endemism, and if so is it specific to Dorn-Dürkheim in the late Miocene? Why are there so many megaherbivores? The late Miocene has been shown to present a latitudinal faunal differentiation, either for large (Costeur and Legendre 2008a) or small mammals (Maridet et al. 2007); it has also been shown to be dominated by modern types of mammals after the late early–middle Miocene turnover changing the whole European fauna. How does Dorn-Dürkheim fit into this scheme?

Dorn-Dürkheim was found in a fluvial formation above the classical Vallesian Dinotheriensande Formation now known as the Eppelsheim Formation which yielded many fossil mammal-bearing localities. This latter formation has recently been shown to be deeply reworked and to show a mixture of middle and late Miocene taxa (Böhme et al. 2012; Pickford and Pourabrishami 2013, this issue). The very nature of the sediment at Dorn-Dürkheim would also raise the attention on possible reworking. This question will be approached in this contribution since some, but only a few, species do not seem to fit well into the Turolian context.

The continental late Miocene in Europe follows the late middle Miocene worldwide cooling event and sees a progressive climatic degradation after a period of washhouse climates in the middle Miocene (the Middle Miocene Climate Optimum; Böhme 2003; Böhme et al. 2008). In this respect, late Miocene faunas often reflect more open environments than what was previously prevailing in the tropical middle Miocene world. Although a number of exceptions exist in the early late Miocene (e.g. Can Llobateres in Spain, or Rudabanya in Hungary) the later European ecosystems seem to be less dominated by forest habitats. Turolian southeastern environments being typical woodlands under a seasonal climate (e.g. Solounias et al. 1999; Spassov 2002; Spassov et al. 2006), it is interesting to

learn what more northern environments were like and in turn understand if latitudinal gradients were an important component of the late Miocene European climate.

With its high diversity and presence of numerous forest dwellers (e.g. *Blackia*, *Pliopetes*, *Miopetaurista*, or *Pliopetaurista*), Dorn-Dürkheim's fauna was always considered to reflect a closed forest environment with a certain level of humidity, or at least with the presence of large stretches of water for its insectivores and beavers to live in (Franzen and Storch 1999). No real in-depth analysis of the fauna at the community level has ever been attempted to confirm this first interpretation based on elements of the mammalian spectrum. The aim of this paper is thus to investigate the fauna by qualitatively and quantitatively analysing its composition and structure (i.e. body masses of the constituting species) and then comparing it to extant ecosystems.

Materials and methods

Fauna

Almost 9000 fossil mammal remains have been discovered in Dorn-Dürkheim (Franzen 2013a, this issue). Several groups were published in a monograph in 1997 as well as in other papers in the last four decades: a first report on carnivores, proboscideans and rodents (Franzen and Storch 1975), insectivores (Storch 1978; Storch and Dahlmann 2000), a complete account on carnivores (Morlo 1997; Roth and Morlo 1997), proboscideans without deinotheres (Gaziry 1997), equids (Bernor and Franzen 1997; Kaiser et al. 2003), rhinocerotids (Cerdeño 1997), suids (van der Made 1997) and bovids (Gentry and Kaiser 2009). A number of groups have remained unstudied such as the Cervidae, the Moschidae, the Deinotheriidae or the Chalicotheriidae and Tapiridae. Some other mammals remain unstudied for the time being (Soricidae, Chiroptera, Lagomorpha, Eomyidae). Figure 1 presents the composition of the mammal assemblage known so far at Dorn-Dürkheim. Biogeography and temporal distribution of the fossil species present at Dorn Dürkheim come from the NOW database (Fortelius 2003) and from a database assembled by the authors (Costeur 2005; Maridet 2003) and available on request.

Settings

The geological settings of the discoveries at Dorn-Dürkheim are detailed in Franzen and Storch (1975) and Franzen (1997, 2013a, this issue). The extent of the Eppelsheim Formation (“Dinotheriensande”) in the region led the discoverers of fossils at Dorn-Dürkheim to the conclusion that the locality would also belong to this formation. The fluvial origin of the fine sands could also confirm this possibility. But later

Fig. 1 Pie diagram of the Dorn-Dürkheim 1 fauna. *Erinaceom.* Erinaceomorpha; *Chirop.* Chiroptera; *Lagom.* Lagomorpha

discoveries of rodents indicated that the locality was Turolian in age and could more specifically be ascribed to biozone MN11. Generally, the Dinotheriensande are known to be reworked (Böhme et al. 2012). The presence of Aquitanian shark teeth and gastropods confirms reworking in Dorn-Dürkheim (Franzen and Storch 1975; and Franzen 2013b, this issue; Franzen et al. 2013, this issue). Franzen and Storch (1975), however, noticed, based on a careful physical analysis of preserved remains, that even if reworking did occur at Dorn-Dürkheim, most of the constituent species do not hint at large reworking. As far as the mammalian assemblage is concerned, the presence of *Dinosorex* sp. for instance is doubtful, because its subfamily (Heterosoricinae) is supposed to have disappeared after MN9, although its persistence in some refuge areas during the late Miocene is also possible. Anyway, most of the taxa found in Dorn-Dürkheim fit with a correlation to the MN11 zone and no obvious evidence of reworking has been otherwise observed (Franzen et al 2013, this issue). We consequently see no impediment to interpreting the mammalian faunal spectrum of Dorn-Dürkheim as a homogeneous assemblage, as well as attempting to decipher its palaeoenvironment.

Cenogram and Principal Component Analysis of body masses

The cenogram methodology has been applied to Dorn-Dürkheim's mammalian fauna. This method is now well known and has been used in various contributions about Eurasian Cenozoic faunas (e.g. Bonis et al. 1992; Costeur et al. 2012a, b; Deng 2009; Legendre 1986, 1989; Montuire 1999; Montuire and Marcolini 2001). The method relies upon estimating body masses of non-flying herbivore mammal species and plotting them on a log-scaled diagram in order to obtain a body mass profile of the whole "community". As individual body mass is a fundamental biological and ecological parameter and participates in structuring mammalian communities, rank-ordered body mass distributions of the species of a community have been shown to give much insight into community structure and also into the environments inhabited by the community (Legendre 1986, 1989). Teeth measurements are needed to estimate body masses of individual species, and especially the surface of the lower first molar (m1) proved to be efficient (Legendre 1989). Most body masses for Dorn-Dürkheim were taken from the literature (including previously published literature

Table 1 List of species classified in their order and family; body masses are given in grams with information on data provenance

Order	Family	Species	Body mass (g)	Reference
Erinaceomorpha	Erinaceidae	<i>Lanthanotherium sanmigueli</i>	99.6	Teeth measurements from Viladecavalls (Agustí et al. 1985)
		<i>Schizogalerix</i> sp.	76.0	Teeth measurements from Kohfidisch (Bachmayer and Wilson 1980)
	Dimylidae	<i>Plesiodimylus</i> cf. <i>chantrei</i>	25.5	Teeth measurements from Belchatow A (Kowalski 1990)
Soricomorpha	Desmanidae	<i>Archaeodesmana vinea</i>	181.3	Storch 1978
		<i>Desmanella rietscheli</i>	53.4	Storch and Dahlmann 2000
		<i>Desmanella</i> sp.	46.3	Storch 1978
	Soricidae	<i>Dinosorex</i> sp.	230.8	Storch 1978
		<i>Crusafontina kormosi</i>	95.5	Storch 1978
	Talpidae	<i>Talpa gilothi</i>	28.1	Teeth measurements from Ambérieu 1 (Farjanel and Mein 1984)
		<i>Talpa vallesensis</i>	27.2	Teeth measurements from Terrassa (Alcalá and Montoya 1991)
Chiroptera	indet.	indet.	–	
		indet.	–	
Lagomorpha	indet.	indet.	–	
		indet.	–	
Rodentia	Anomalomyidae	<i>Pterospalax</i> sp.	45.0	Estimate
		<i>Prospalax petteri</i>	44.5	Franzen and Storch 1975
	Castoridae	<i>Castor neglectus</i>	11,081.0	Teeth measurements from Pont de Gail (Ginsburg 1975)
		<i>Chalicomys jaegeri</i>	6,947.0	Teeth measurements from Ambérieu 1 (Farjanel and Mein 1984)
		<i>Chalicomys plassi</i>	6,550.0	Average <i>Chalicomys</i> (Costeur 2005)
		<i>Dipoides problematicus</i>	2,414.4	Franzen and Storch 1975
		<i>Trogotherium minutum rhenanum</i>	1,264.5	Franzen and Storch 1975
		<i>Cricetodon</i> sp.	43.5	Franzen and Storch 1975
	Cricetidae	<i>Neocricetodon</i> cf. <i>lavocati</i>	37.8	Average <i>Neocricetodon</i> (Costeur 2005)
		<i>Epimeriones austriacus</i>	26.3	Franzen and Storch 1975
		<i>Collimys primus</i>	20.7	Franzen and Storch 1975
	Eomyidae	<i>Leptodontomys</i> sp.	5.1	Average <i>L. catalaunicus</i> in Valles Penedes Basin (Costeur 2005)
		<i>Keramidomys</i> sp.	3.7	Teeth measurements from Anwil (Engesser 1972)
	Gliridae	<i>Glis</i> cf. <i>minor</i>	72.8	Teeth measurements from Panska Góra (Bednarczyk 1993)
		<i>Muscardinus vireti</i>	37.2	Teeth measurements from Lissieu (Mein 1999)
		<i>Microdyromys</i> sp.	9.0	Teeth measurements from Belchatow A (Kowalski 1990)
		<i>Parapodemus lugdunensis</i>	22.3	Franzen and Storch 1975
	Sciuridae	<i>Miopetaurista</i> sp.	980.6	Teeth measurements from Can Llobateres (Hartenberger and Crusafont 1979)
		<i>Pliopetaurista bressana</i>	218.9	Teeth measurements from Ambérieu 3 (Mein 1970)
		<i>Spermophilinus</i> sp.	148.5	Franzen and Storch 1975
		<i>Pliopetes</i> sp.	120.0	Estimate
		<i>Blackia</i> sp.	24.3	Franzen and Storch 1975
	Zapodidae	<i>Eozapus</i> sp.	15.2	Teeth measurement <i>E. intermedius</i> from Puente Minero (Alcalá et al. 1991)
Carnivora	Ursidae	<i>Simocyon</i> sp.	55,000	NOW

Table 1 (continued)

Order	Family	Species	Body mass (g)	Reference
	Mustelidae	<i>Eomellivora wimani</i>	45,000	NOW
		<i>Taxodon</i> sp.	3,000	NOW
		<i>Promeles palaeatticus</i>	6,500	NOW
		<i>Baranogale</i> cf. <i>adroveri</i>	2,000	NOW
		? <i>Circamustela</i> sp.	1,700	NOW
		<i>Martes</i> cf. <i>sansaniensis</i>	6,000	NOW
		? <i>Martes</i> sp.	2,000	NOW
		Mustelinae indet.	–	
	Mustelinae indet.	–		
	Hyaenidae	<i>Adcrocuta eximia</i>	70,000	NOW
		<i>Protictitherium crassum</i>	6,500	NOW
		<i>Thalassictis robusta</i>	20,000	NOW
		<i>Allohyaena kadici</i>	75,000	NOW
		“ <i>Dinocrocuta</i> sp.”	100,000	NOW
	Felidae	<i>Felis attica</i>	9,000	NOW
		<i>Paramachaerodus orientalis</i>	58,000	NOW
		“ <i>Paramachaerodus ogygius</i> ”	44,000	NOW
		<i>Machairodus</i> cf. <i>aphanistus</i>	160,000	NOW
	Ursidae	<i>Ursavus primaevus</i>	90,000	NOW
		<i>Ursavus depereti</i>	100,000	NOW
		<i>Indarctos arctoides</i>	160,000	NOW
		<i>Indarctos atticus atticus</i>	350,000	NOW
Proboscidea	Deinotheriidae	<i>Deinotherium proavum</i>	15,000,000.0	Estimate
	Elephantidae	<i>Stegotetrabelodon lehmanni</i>	8,560,051.4	Gaziry 1997
		<i>Anancus arvernensis tuoliensis</i>	5,000,000.0	Estimate
		<i>Stegolophodon caementifer</i>	5,000,000.0	Estimate
		<i>Tetralophodon atticus</i>	2,829,241.0	Teeth measurements from Eppelsheim (Tobien 1980)
Perissodactyla	Equidae	“ <i>Hippotherium primigenium</i> ”	200,000.0	Estimate (Kaiser et al. 2003)
		<i>Hippotherium kammerschmittae</i>	190,000.0	Estimate (Kaiser et al. 2003)
	Chalicotheriidae	<i>Anisodon</i> sp.	453,632.4	Fahlke et al. this issue
	Rhinocerotidae	<i>Dihoplus</i> cf. <i>schleiermacheri</i>	2,433,185.0	Teeth measurements from Eppelsheim (Guérin 1980)
		<i>Aceratherium incisivum</i>	2,186,679.0	Teeth measurements from Can Llobateres
		<i>Alicornops alfambrense</i>	1,977,538.0	Average <i>A. incisivum</i> (Costeur 2005)
	Tapiridae	<i>Tapirus priscus</i>	262,538.0	Teeth measurements from Eppelsheim (Guérin and Eisenmann 1994)
		<i>Tapiriscus pannonicus</i>	200,000.0	Estimate
Cetartiodactyla	Bovidae	Bovidae sp.2 sensu Gentry & Kaiser	228,646.7	Gentry and Kaiser 2009
		Bovidae sp.3 sensu Gentry & Kaiser	–	
		<i>Miotragocerus</i> sp.	66,940.3	Gentry and Kaiser 2009
	Cervidae	cf. <i>Cervavitus mimus</i>	50,000.0	Estimate
		<i>Procapreolus</i> sp.	43,474.0	Azanza et al. this issue
		Muntiacini indet.	24,979.0	Azanza et al. this issue
	Moschidae	<i>Micromeryx</i> sp.	5,223.6	Aiglstorfer and Costeur this issue
	Suidae	<i>Microstonyx</i>	262,555.8	van der Made 1997
			(“ <i>Hippopotamodon</i> ”) <i>major</i>	
	Tragulidae	<i>Dorcatherium nauii</i>	31,373.0	Teeth measurements from Eppelsheim

on Dorn-Dürkheim) while some were measured by participants at the meeting dedicated to the fauna in June 2012. Some body masses could not be estimated with material from Dorn-Dürkheim simply because not all species preserved an ml; in this case, data from the same species in other localities close in time and/or space were used (see Table 1). This is not a limiting factor since body masses estimated that way represent species means and not individual measurements (Legendre 1989). Body masses are given in Table 1.

Our analysis of the cenogram involves comparing the “large” and “small” mammal segments of the cenogram, with a limit at 8 kg. This proved to be interesting. Indeed, cenogram parameters such as the gap in body masses at 8 kg seem to be correlated to mean annual precipitation (MAP) levels (Costeur and Legendre 2008b). The latter are indirect good indicators for vegetation density: the smaller the 8-kg gap, the higher the MAP.

Both indeterminate lagomorphs are not represented on the cenogram because of difficulties in reconstructing body masses of extinct species.

As already proposed (Costeur et al. 2012a, b), a principal component analysis (PCA) of the proportions of six body mass categories calculated for Dorn-Dürkheim and for a sample of extant faunas from Legendre (1989) was run using software PAST (Hammer et al. 2001). Body mass categories are adapted from Holling (1992) and extracted for each fauna (1–10 g, 10–100 g, 100–1,000 g, 1–10 kg, 10–1,000 kg and >1,000 kg). Raw proportion data for both extant and extinct samples are available on request (the extant dataset is published in Costeur et al. 2012a, b, Dorn-Dürkheim has proportions of 5.6, 35.2, 11.1, 9.3, 24.1, and 14.8 %, respectively). Raw body masses and faunal lists of extant faunas are found in Legendre (1989) and in an extended dataset available upon request.

Body mass estimates were also gathered for the Carnivora to investigate their position in the overall mammalian community. The data come from the Neogene of the Old World (NOW) database (Fortelius 2003) and are given in Table 1 along with body masses for the other mammals.

Theoretical biomasses of primary and secondary consumers

Body mass data for primary and secondary consumers were then used to reconstruct theoretical abundances of the different taxa and in turn theoretical biomasses for both categories of preys and predators. The method follows that of Meloro and Clauss (2012). Theoretical biomasses for a range of African ecosystems were calculated for extant faunas (Fig. 4) in order to broaden the spectrum of Meloro and Clauss (2012), which only considered savanna environments. We only compare Dorn-Dürkheim’s data to African ecosystems since we do not

want to mix too much information related to specific evolutionary histories or geographic patterns (e.g. absence of very large mammals in South America, island rules, etc.). This will instead be the scope of another contribution. On theoretical and empirical grounds (amount of forest inhabitants and moist-adapted species in Dorn-Dürkheim), it is highly unlikely that a late Miocene fauna would be close to a steppe or dry forest; thus, such environments present in Asia have not been included in the analysis. Previous work (Costeur et al. 2012a, b) has shown that the inclusion of boreal steppe-like northern modern environments created much inertia and blurred the message. Data on body masses in extant faunas come from Legendre (1989). Following the method of Meloro and Clauss (2012) based on data in Hayward et al. (2007), only large predators above 21 kg and herbivores in the range 7–1,000 kg are considered here. As biomass data are rare, this is the only possibility to compare our results with large-scale published results, although we are aware that an in-depth analysis would be interesting, and this will be the scope of another study. The theoretical grounds behind the method are that body mass of a species scales to its abundance (population density), and then biomass of a species can be estimated from the body mass of its individual and population densities, following allometric equations published in Silva and Downing (1995) for different mammalian taxonomic groups or guilds. The aim here is to gain insights into mammalian community structure and dynamics, and in particular for our purpose here to see if relative biomasses of preys and predators have a potential power to classify a fauna within an environment. This constitutes an interesting complementary approach to investigate the structure of mammalian communities (in addition to the cenogram and related PCA) and to further interpret the palaeoenvironmental and palaeoecological characteristics of a given fossil fauna.

Results

Fauna

Dorn-Dürkheim’s fauna contains at least 79 species of mammals (some are still indeterminate). It has about 64 genera, 29 families and 9 orders (Fig. 1). The richest order is the Rodentia which contributes a little more than 29 % of the whole fauna followed by Carnivora representing more than 26 % of the total number of species. Perissodactyla and Artiodactyla contain 10.1 and 11.4 % of Dorn-Dürkheim’s species, respectively, and the 5 species of Proboscidea represent 6.3 % of the

fauna. Soricomorpha and Erinaceomorpha total 11.4 % of the fauna, while the indeterminate Chiroptera and Lagomorpha each contain 2 species and thus 2.5 % of the fauna. When compared to other Turolian faunas, Dorn-Dürkheim is the richest in MN11.

The biogeography of the different species is described here. As far as small mammals are concerned, starting with erinaceomorphs and soricomorphs, an unidentified species of genus *Schizogalerix* is present in Dorn-Dürkheim. This genus is mainly found in the late Miocene of Northern and Central Europe (Germany, Austria, France, and Switzerland); however, it is also known in the middle and late Miocene of Greece and Anatolia. *Lanthanotherium sanmigueli* is also widespread in the early and middle late Miocene of Western Europe (MN9–11; Austria, France, Spain, Germany, Portugal). *Plesiodimylus chantrei* shows an especially broad temporal and geographic record in Europe. It is known from the early Miocene (MN4) until the middle late Miocene (MN11). In addition to the conferred form of Dorn-Dürkheim, it has also been found in other localities of the late Miocene of Germany, Austria, France, Hungary, Poland and Spain.

Crusafontina kormosi has a similar temporal distribution but seems to have a slightly more restricted geographical distribution than *Lanthanotherium sanmigueli*, mainly from the late Miocene of France, Austria, Germany and Hungary. *Archaeodesmana vinea* was initially described from Dorn-Dürkheim as a subspecies of *Desmana pontica* (Storch 1978), after which it has been encountered in several late Miocene localities from France and Austria (MN9–11).

Desmanella rietscheli was also described from Dorn-Dürkheim (Storch and Dahlmann 2000), and the species has so far only been identified in the late Miocene of Germany and Austria. *Talpa vallesiensis* is a primarily Iberian taxon as it has been identified in several Spanish localities of the Early late Miocene. It is, however, also present in Dorn-Dürkheim and Schernham (Austria, MN10). By contrast, *Talpa gilothi* (of which Dorn-Dürkheim is the type locality) seems absent from the southernmost European fossil record; it is also known from several late Miocene French localities (MN10–13) and from the late Miocene of Austria (MN11). Three teeth from Dorn-Dürkheim have been attributed by Storch (1978) to an indeterminate species of *Dinosorex*. Assuming that this attribution to the genus *Dinosorex* is correct, these specimens would represent the latest record of Heterosoricinae in Europe, whereas this subfamily is usually considered to have gone extinct at the end of the Vallesian (MN9).

For most of the above-mentioned Erinaceomorpha and Soricomorpha (*L. sanmigueli*, *P. chantrei*, *C. kormosi*, *A. vinea*, *D. rietscheli*, *T. vallesiensis* and *T. gilothi*), their respective occurrence in Dorn-Dürkheim (MN11) is one of the latest in the European fossil record.

Rodents are abundant in Dorn-Dürkheim comprising a little less than a third of the whole fauna.

An indeterminate species of *Spermophilinus* has been identified in Dorn-Dürkheim. Four species of *Spermophilinus* are known in Europe, three of them belonging to the same lineage (*S. besana*–*S. bredai*–*S. turolensis*) known from the early Miocene to the early Pliocene and recognised almost everywhere in Europe. Likewise, genus *Miopetaurista*, also present in Dorn-Dürkheim, is widespread in Europe and known from the early Miocene to the Pliocene. The genus *Blackia* is known in Europe since the early Miocene; however, it becomes more widely distributed in the late Miocene (Austria, Germany, Czech Republic, France, Switzerland, Hungary), but remains restricted to northern regions. By contrast, genus *Pliopetes* presents a much more restricted temporal and geographical distribution from the middle late Miocene to the early Pliocene of Austria, Poland, France and Germany. *Pliopetaurista bressana* has been identified in several late Miocene localities from France (MN10–11) and in Austria (MN11). Consequently, this species seems to have a very restricted temporal and geographical distribution; it has, however, also been mentioned in Greece (Levkon, MN10).

Among the five beavers found in Dorn-Dürkheim, *Dipoides problematicus*, *Chalicomys jaegeri* and *Trogontherium minutum* present a very large temporal and geographical distribution in the whole of Europe. However, the subspecies *T. minutum rhenanum* is only known from the late Miocene of France and Germany (MN10–11). By contrast, *Castor neglectus* is quite poorly recorded and has only been found in the early late Miocene of Germany and Moldavia in addition to Dorn-Dürkheim. *Chalicomys plassi* of which Dorn-Dürkheim is the type locality has so far never been discovered elsewhere (Hugueney 1999) and seems to be truly endemic to Dorn-Dürkheim, although Storch (in Franzen and Storch 1975) stated that some material ascribed to *Steneofiber eseri* in other localities may actually belong to *C. plassi*.

Epimeriones austriacus is also rare in the European fossil record and seems restricted to Northern Europe; it is only known so far from the late Miocene and early Pliocene from Germany, France, Austria and Poland.

Among cricetids, both late Miocene taxa *Neocricetodon lavocati* and *Collimys primus* are poorly represented in the European fossil record; *N. lavocati* was discovered in some localities from France, Greece and Spain, whereas *C. primus* is only recorded in the late Miocene of Germany and Austria. The third cricetid is an indeterminate *Cricetulodon*, of which most of the species are Southern European inhabitants (e.g. *C. sabadellensis*, *C. hartenbergeri*, *C. meini*, *C. lucentensis*), although the genus can be found in more northern regions (e.g. *C. bugesiensis*). *Prospalax petteri* is present in Europe

from the early to middle late Miocene (MN9–11); it is restricted to northern and northeastern regions (France, Germany, Austria, Hungary).

Parapodemus lugdunensis is limited to the early/middle late Miocene fossil record but can be found in all European regions and in Anatolia.

Eozapus sp. is the only zaptodid taxon found in Dorn-Dürkheim. *E. intermedius* is so far the only species known in the late Miocene of Europe for the genus. The species itself has been found in various regions of Europe (Austria, Spain, Germany, and Czech Rep.), and the genus has also been mentioned in the late Miocene of Turkey (Sümmen et al. 1989).

Muscardinus vireti and affine forms have been found in several late Miocene localities of Spain, France and Italy; its occurrence in Dorn-Dürkheim constitutes one of the earliest and northernmost records of this species in Europe.

The occurrence of *Glis minor* in Dorn-Dürkheim, Kohfidisch (MN11) and Rudabánya (MN9) are the earliest records of this species in the late Miocene of Europe; the geographical distribution of the species seems rather limited at that time. Later, *G. minor* is recorded in several localities from the latest Miocene and Pliocene of Northern and Central Europe (Germany, Austria, Hungary, and Poland) and has also been mentioned in the Pliocene of Southern France (Bachelet et al. 1990) and Turkey (Ünay and de Bruijn 1998).

The genus *Microdyromys* is also present in Dorn-Dürkheim, if on the one hand the genus was widespread and abundant in the early and middle Miocene of Europe, it is on the other hand quite rare in the late Miocene record. In addition to Germany, it has, however, been mentioned in the late Miocene of France, Switzerland, Spain and Poland.

One of the two eomyids discovered in Dorn-Dürkheim, indeterminate at the specific level, was identified as belonging to genus *Leptodontomys* (a genus initially described from the Miocene of North America). As demonstrated by Prieto (2012), the differentiation between genera *Leptodontomys* and *Eomyops* is mainly in mandible and incisor characteristics. It is consequently difficult to differentiate them based on isolated teeth. It is, however, noteworthy that most of the occurrences of this type of eomyid in Europe are ascribed to genus *Eomyops* rather than *Leptodontomys* (e.g. Daxner-Höck and Höck 2009), and we consequently follow this point of view in the present study. Both *Eomyops* and *Keramidomys* appear in Europe at the end of the early Miocene (MN5), although eomyids are generally rarer in the Late Miocene fossil record, and these genera have been found in several localities from Spain, Germany, Poland, Hungary, Austria, France, Switzerland and Greece.

To summarise, among the 32 identified small mammals from Dorn-Dürkheim, about half of them are geographically restricted to Northern and Central Europe which supports

the strong biogeographical differentiation observed between northern and southern regions in the late Miocene of Europe (Maridet et al. 2007). In the late Miocene small mammal fossil record, the faunas of Eichkogel (MN11) and Kohfidisch (MN11) are the closest in terms of composition to Dorn-Dürkheim.

Large herbivorous mammals show a combination of widespread species with a long duration and more restricted ones. *Deinotherium proavum* spans the late middle to late Miocene. *Anancus arvernensis* has its first European occurrence in Dorn-Dürkheim, but then spread across Europe and occurs throughout the Pliocene. The other two proboscideans, *Stegolophodon caementifer* and *Stegotetralodon lehmanni*, are restricted to Dorn-Dürkheim. Markov (2008) indicated that neither species was valid and cited an unpublished work (Metz-Müller 2000 in Markov 2008) to back-up this hypothesis. Both species would be attributable to *Tetralophodon atticus* and *Anancus* sp., respectively (or *A. lehmanni* according to priority rules cited by Markov 2008). As no detailed revision of the material was ever published, we prefer to be conservative and keep these two genera and species in the faunal list, although we are aware that much caution should be taken when referring to them. Both horses show a very different distribution pattern, with the cosmopolitan “*Hippotherium primigenium*” spanning the whole late Miocene and being found almost everywhere especially in MN9 and MN10, in association with the endemic *Hippotherium kammerschmittae*, which is only found in Dorn-Dürkheim. It is to be noted that recent usage prefers referring to *H. brachypus* rather than to *H. primigenium* for post-Vallesian large hipparionine horses (see, for instance, Kaya et al. 2012). As the material of the large *Hippotherium* from Dorn-Dürkheim has not been reviewed since Kaiser et al. (2003), we will still refer to this species name pending taxonomical revision. The chalicothere *Anisodon* has a record starting in the middle Miocene of France and has a reduced presence in the late Miocene as *Chalicotherium* became dominant. Its late Miocene presence is attested in the Iberian Peninsula but with very few records. Its presence in Dorn-Dürkheim with many fossil remains is thus very peculiar (see Fahlke et al. 2013, this issue). For both tapirs the time range was extended to MN9-12 and MN9-11 for *Tapiriscus pannonicus* and *Tapirus priscus*, respectively (Franzen 2013b). They both have a Central to Western European distribution. *Dihoplus* cf. *schleiermacheri* and *Aceratherium incisivum* occur during all the late Miocene throughout Europe. By contrast, *Alicornops alfambrense* is a very rare rhinoceros occurring in only two, possibly three, localities, the first one being its type locality, La Roma 2 in Spain (MN10), and the others being Dorn-Dürkheim 1 (Cerdeño 1997) and possibly Montredon in France (MN10; see Cerdeño 1997). As far as artiodactyls are concerned, the suid *Hippopotamodon* (“*Microstonyx*”)

major is also a well-known species of the European late Miocene with a peak of geographic distribution in the Turolian; it is often referred to as *Microstonyx major* by several authors (Kostopoulos et al. 2001), but the latter seems to be a junior synonym of the former (Pickford 1988). Kostopoulos et al. (2001) also recognise the proximity of the two genera and point to the necessity of detailed comparisons. *Dorcatherium navi* (if it is really *D. navi*; the material has not yet been revised) is also a well-known component of the middle to late Miocene faunas, up to its last appearance datum in MN12. The other artiodactyls are less well known; the cervid cf. *Cervavitus mimus* is still an enigmatic taxon restricted to biozone MN11 that would need to be revised. *Procapreolus* is known mostly after MN11 (with an Austrian record in MN9; Fortelius 2003). The third cervid is an indeterminate Muntiacinae (see Azanza et al. 2013, this issue). A moschid is now described from Dorn-Dürkheim and ascribed to *Micromeryx* sp. (Aiglstorfer and Costeur 2013, this issue). It represents one of the last occurrences for this long-lasting genus (appearing in MN5, and last occurring in a small number of localities in MN11). The bovids of Dorn-Dürkheim were not easily identifiable and only *Miotragocerus* sp. could be attributed with certainty to a known taxon. *Miotragocerus* has a large presence in the early late Miocene but fades rapidly towards the end of the period. The other two bovids are indeterminate (Gentry and Kaiser 2009).

Carnivores have been extensively discussed in Morlo (1997) and Roth and Morlo (1997). Dorn-Dürkheim also appears to be a rich fauna in terms of Carnivora with a diverse community of cosmopolitan and more restricted taxa, or taxa that were already present in Europe before MN11 and taxa that occur there for the first time (like *Promeles* and *Baranogale* for instance; Morlo 1997). More taxonomical work would be welcome on the carnivores of Dorn-Dürkheim since a number of forms have been revised in other localities. Salesa et al. (2010) revised the genus *Paramachaerodus* and transferred the species *P. ogygius* into the genus *Promegantereon* and species *Promegantereon ogygia*. Until a reassessment of the material is carried out, we will keep the material of Dorn-Dürkheim under "*Paramachaerodus ogygius*".

Palaeoenvironmental inferences based on mammal body masses

Cenogram

Dorn-Dürkheim's cenogram shows a long suite of species, with more than 50 species of non-flying mammals able to be plotted. The overall shape of the body mass distribution is quite continuous but with some breaks and gaps (Fig. 2). The gap at the theoretical 8 kg limit (see "Materials and methods", and Costeur and Legendre 2008b) is very small

Fig. 2 Cenogram of the Dorn-Dürkheim 1 fauna with body masses (grams) in Log scale on the *y* coordinate and rank order of the species on the *x* coordinate. The grey solid line gives a schematic view of the cenogram segments and the double grey arrow points at the mid-sizes gap

(0.2 in log value) which would indicate rather humid conditions (high MAP), but a closer look at other characteristics of the cenogram gives more details and does not contradict with a small gap at 8 kg. The slope of the segment representing mammals roughly above 1 kg is visually different from that of those below this threshold value (slopes have not been quantified since quantification does not really help predict climatic parameters in this case; Legendre 1989). Altogether, these observations differ from very continuous distributions without any break that are found in truly closed environments (Legendre 1989). This leads to the interpretation that the environment was not fully closed, contrary to what has often been proposed in the past (Franzen and Storch 1975, 1999). More recent analyses of the ecology of Dorn-Dürkheim's horses (Kaiser et al. 2003) has lent credence to this assumption. The long suite of mammals would still indicate a strong presence of closed areas in a rather humid context, but forest inhabitants in the middle sizes often blur a cenogram's message and hide the visibility of more open areas in the landscape (Travouillon and Legendre 2009).

PCA

A principal component analysis run on six size categories (see "Materials and methods") in comparison with today's ecosystems clusters Dorn-Dürkheim with tropical grasslands to woodlands, also indicating that the environment was probably not that closed. There is obviously some uncertainty, since biome types show a large amount of overlap but Dorn-Dürkheim clusters rather far from truly forested environments (Fig. 3). The amount of very large species at Dorn-Dürkheim is certainly important here and drags the fauna towards more open environments. The closest faunas clustering with Dorn-Dürkheim in the PCA indeed include South African tropical savannas (Transvaal province) and/or woodlands (Ethiopia and Democratic Republic of

Fig. 3 Distribution of faunas on the two first axes of the principal component analysis based on the distribution of weights within the categories 1–10 g, 10–100 g, 100–1,000 g, 1–10 kg, 10–1,000 kg and

>1,000 kg, for the extant faunas and for Dorn-Dürkheim 1. **a** Raw data; **b** empirical clouds representing simplified biome types

Congo). The latter show mean annual precipitations around 400–700 mm (up to about 1,300 mm for the Democratic Republic of Congo ecosystem) and are vast areas of open landscapes with many isolated to interconnected scrub or woodland patches. The South African and Ethiopian faunas are at middle altitudes around 1,200 m whereas the Congo one is lower at 600 m altitude. This probably also plays a role, together with higher latitude, in the relatively lower amount of

precipitations received while compared to the Democratic Republic of Congo fauna.

Theoretical biomasses

A comparison of the fossil fauna with theoretical predator/prey biomasses calculated for extant African biomes ranging from tropical rainforest to deserts via tropical savannas was

Fig. 4 Log–Log scatterplot of mammal herbivores and predators estimated biomasses for 74 extant faunas and Dorn-Dürkheim 1. The range ellipses are drawn, for six of the biome types, at a confidence level of 95 %. *N* Number of extant faunas for each biome type

Environmental categories :

- | | |
|------------------------------------|---|
| □ Tropical rainforest (N=11) | ○ Tropical savanna-desert (N=7) |
| △ Tropical seasonal forest (N=4) | ○ Desert (N=10) |
| △ Tropical savanna-woodland (N=13) | ◇ Mediterranean vegetation (N=3) |
| △ Tropical savanna-scrub (N=21) | ◆ Temperate forest-grassland-woodland (N=3) |
| ▲ Tropical savanna (N=2) | ★ Dorn-Dürkheim 1 |

95% confidence range ellipses :

- | | |
|-----------------------------|---------------------------|
| ○ Tropical rainforest | ○ Tropical savanna-scrub |
| ○ Tropical seasonal forest | ○ Tropical savanna-desert |
| ○ Tropical savanna-woodland | ○ Desert |

carried out. The very high predator biomass of species above 21 kg (sensu Meloro and Clauss 2012), together with the high biomass of herbivore species in the 7–1,000 kg range, cluster Dorn-Dürkheim with tropical savannas and woodlands of today’s Africa (Fig. 4). This is far from the data found in tropical rainforest or most temperate forested environments (Fig. 4). It fits remarkably well with the PCA run on the body mass categories. In addition, this preliminary analysis shows that African ecosystems can be relatively well separated when the biomasses of their constituent mammal species are analysed. And then fossil data can in turn be included in the analysis to trace back the palaeoenvironments. Meloro and Clauss (2012) analysed their fossil faunas in considering either herbivores in the 7–450 kg range or herbivores in the 7–1,000 kg range. The second set of the analysis yielded different results from the first one in that mammals in the range 450–1,000 kg tended not to be part of the carnivores’ diets. They concluded that the ecosystems showing this body mass range were more likely to be bottom-up controlled than top-down controlled. Our body mass data for Dorn-Dürkheim shows a single mammal species in this 450–1,000 kg size range (*Anisodon* sp. with an estimated body mass of 453 kg) and thus no significant difference is evidenced if one calculates both theoretical biomasses (e.g. 7–450 kg and 7–1,000 kg:

theoretical biomasses of 3.2 or 3.28 in Log value, respectively). The fauna was thus probably more top-down controlled as in recent African savanna ecosystems (Meloro and Clauss 2012), e.g. predators partly controlling their prey community structure (Terborgh et al. 1999). Another interesting insight is into the high predator biomass (for carnivores above 21 kg) in Dorn-Dürkheim. In African ecosystems, tropical rainforests or desert environments generally show lower large carnivore biomasses (this does not hold any more when smaller carnivores are included; analysis not shown here; personal observations) compared to woodlands or savannas. Large predators are more abundant in more open environments and this gives much insight into the interpretation of fossil faunas.

Discussion

Dorn-Dürkheim’s rich Turolian fauna has always been thought to reflect closed forested habitats, giving grounds to hypotheses of a northern much more forested Europe. Our results do not confirm this hypothesis and refine our understanding of the complexity of the landscape in the Turolian of Northern Europe. Several faunal peculiarities and a more detailed idea of the palaeoenvironment arise from our analysis.

Biogeographic affinities

The European Turolian, especially in the northern regions, is less diversified than the middle Miocene as a whole. This reflects the ongoing process that started after the Middle Miocene Climatic Optimum, showing a global cooling trend over the late Miocene (see Costeur and Legendre 2008a for large mammal diversity over the Neogene). The very low number of bovids found at Dorn-Dürkheim is typical for late Miocene northern regions in great contrast with south-eastern Europe where they thrive, representing more than a quarter of the total number of species in the Greek–Iranian bioprovince (Bonis et al. 1992; Costeur and Legendre 2008a). By contrast, more northern regions have more cervids, probably accounting for different environments. A nice biogeographic pattern arises with large and cosmopolitan ungulate species yielding biogeographic affinities between Dorn-Dürkheim’s region in MN11 and southwestern regions (Iberian Peninsula up to Central France), while more restricted small species show only relatively close affinities between the German region and Central France (Costeur et al. 2004; Maridet et al. 2007). This is worth noting when one wants to decipher biogeographic patterns, that species with high dispersal abilities and lower adaptations to local habitats (generally in the large sizes) do not yield the same picture as smaller-sized species which often have lower dispersal capacities and higher habitat-related specialisations, and thus generally a smaller minimum geographic range (Gaston 2003). Likewise, the faunal composition of Dorn-Dürkheim 1 at the family level reflects northern affinities with an even balance between cervids and bovids, few murids and still well represented by glirids and cricetids (Maridet et al. 2013). Genus-based faunal similarities (Eronen et al. 2009) using the same methodology as the species-based analyses performed on ungulates and rodents (Costeur et al. 2004; Maridet et al. 2007) give different results and probably fail to catch finer biogeographic patterns. Dorn-Dürkheim 1 would then be very close to the Pikermian Greek fauna although the faunal lists largely differ, including important characteristics of the faunal structure.

Diversity of Castoridae

A number of peculiarities make Dorn-Dürkheim 1 quite exceptional. First, the locality has yielded five species of beavers. To the best of our knowledge, this is a unique situation worldwide. Time averaging could account for this, but even considering this, it is still a rare situation. Fossil beavers could be hypothesised to show different habits from modern beavers, but close dental morphology between Dorn-Dürkheim’s fossil beavers and modern beavers (see Franzen and Storch 1975) calls for similar habits. Besides the fact that beavers have a strong impact on local to

landscape-level geomorphology by building dams that help in trapping huge quantities of sediment in the resulting ponds (Butler and Malanson 2005; Gurnell 1998), and eventually could help accumulate carcasses increasing the recovered biodiversity, they also profoundly affect ecosystem characteristics around their dams (Naiman et al. 1988; Rosell et al. 2005). Indeed, beavers are ecosystem engineers and modify their surrounding environment in clearing riparian forest and creating so-called “beaver meadows”. These more open areas, sometimes partly under water because of water accumulation allowed by the dams, develop as highly diverse and complex zones where a significant amount of total riparian plant diversity can be found. In some cases, beavers can even be responsible for successive floods which can lead, after a few years, to the extinction of local anchored forest to the benefit of scrub and open meadow vegetation (Mitchell and Niering 1993; Sturtevant 1998). With regard to the exceptional coexistence of five species in Dorn-Dürkheim, beaver populations have certainly modified the structure of the riparian zone, and could even have contributed to some extent to the opening and fractioning of the landscapes at a larger scale (Naiman et al. 1988). In turn, as mentioned in Rosell et al. (2005), this creates favourable conditions for species which would otherwise be excluded. Creating favourable conditions (ponds) that increase terrestrial and freshwater invertebrate diversity, stream fish diversity, amphibian/reptile diversity or aquatic birds diversity has a positive effect on predator diversity (birds or semi-aquatic mammals).

Other non-predator semi-aquatic mammals find advantages in exploiting beaver dams and lodges (refuge areas, breeding areas, food supply). In addition, beavers have a positive effect on large mammals because they allow softer vegetation to grow in their meadows, enabling cervids for instance to feed on them (see Rosell et al. 2005 for a thorough review).

Finally, beavers are interesting prey for large carnivores, and large carnivore biomass was indeed high at Dorn-Dürkheim.

Diversity of proboscideans

A further peculiarity is the presence of five species of proboscideans which is also a very rare situation, not encountered in present-day ecosystems. We mentioned the taxonomical problems surrounding *Stegolophodon caementifer* and *Stegotrabelodon lehmanni* (see Markov 2008). If both taxa are indeed not valid, then the proboscidean diversity would drop to three species, which is still high but more in accordance with other Miocene localities. Sansan (middle Miocene, France), for instance, also presents a high proboscidean diversity (Costeur et al. 2012a, b). It has been suggested that the middle Miocene was a period of very high

primary productivity triggered by high atmospheric CO₂ levels able to sustain such a high herbivore biomass completed by other megaherbivore species (Janis et al. 2000). But such a situation would be unique and difficult to explain for a late Miocene northern locality. As Dorn-Dürkheim is known to show some reworking, one could question the validity of this proboscidean assemblage, but no sign of intense reworking in proboscideans was ever observed and the first occurrence of species well distributed later in the Miocene and Pliocene (e.g. *Anancus arvernensis*) seems to disqualify the taphonomical bias hypothesis. The restricted presence of *Stegolophodon caementifer* and *Stegotrabelodon lehmanni* to Dorn-Dürkheim could only also be questioned because very large mammals tend to show few examples of endemism. And Göhlich (1999), and later Markov (2008) (see above), did indeed question the validity of the latter. There is thus maybe some space for taxonomical improvement but not so much as to dramatically decrease Dorn-Dürkheim's proboscidean diversity. On the other hand, Calandra et al. (2008, 2010) showed that several proboscidean species could coexist thanks to resource partitioning, and this could also have applied to even richer localities. Megaherbivores are known to have a profound impact on vegetation; they favour, by trampling, the re-growth of young high nutritional plants on which smaller herbivores feed (Aber and Melillo 2001). Dorn-Dürkheim 1 has a relatively high amount of smaller-sized herbivores that could benefit from this ecological role.

Absence of primates

Another interesting faunal characteristic of Dorn-Dürkheim, although the locality has been extensively sampled for decades, is the absence of primates, and particularly of cercopithecoids (from which only *Mesopithecus* is known in MN11) which are otherwise found in Turolian localities (Koufos et al. 2003; Eronen and Rook 2004; Koufos 2009a, 2009b). No primate species has been found north to the central-eastern French locality Mollon in MN11 (*Mesopithecus* sp.; Mein 1984). Eronen and Rook (2004) seem to indicate that cercopithecoids, together with the other late Miocene primates (hominids and pliopithecids), prefer relatively more humid environments with wooded habitats. This would actually be in good agreement with the reconstructed palaeoenvironmental conditions that prevailed in Dorn-Dürkheim. However, Youlatos and Koufos (2010) infer semi-terrestrial habits for Turolian *Mesopithecus* based on postcranial characteristics, and show that the environments in which the genus lived in the late Miocene were relatively dry open grasslands with limited forest cover, which would not fit that well with the relatively more humid picture we have of Dorn-Dürkheim 1 compared to the southeastern European environments. Taphonomic biases may have prevented the preservation or the finding of primate remains there. However, considering

the general good preservation and abundance of fossil remains in Dorn-Dürkheim, the absence of primates might instead provide further evidence for a restricted geographic distribution during the Turolian (i.e. primates ecologically excluded from northernmost European regions).

Palaeoenvironment and European context

Our results based on body masses in mammals indicate that Dorn-Dürkheim was more of a savanna-scrubland-woodland than a closed humid forest such as has been hypothesised previously (Franzen 1997). Recent ecosystems that cluster close to Dorn-Dürkheim in our PCA of body mass categories show MAP roughly between 500 and 1,200 mm (two faunas from South Africa at 400 and 700 mm, and one fauna in the Democratic Republic of Congo at 1,200 mm). This is in good agreement with MAP estimates derived from other independent sources such as herpetological assemblages in Central Europe (Böhme et al. 2011) or plants (Kern et al. 2012; Utescher et al. 2012). Accordingly, mammal-based Mean Annual Temperature (MAT) estimates converge with plant-based estimates around 14–16 °C (Montuire et al. 2006; Utescher et al. 2012). Recent analyses of morphological traits in mammals led to almost the same conclusions with MAT of around 15 °C for Dorn-Dürkheim 1 (Liu et al. 2012) and MAP somewhat higher, around 1,500 mm, but with barely predictive models that induce a quite large uncertainty (a correlation coefficient of –0.57 for MAP based on average hypsodonty, for instance; Liu et al. 2012). According to this last study, Dorn-Dürkheim 1 would cluster at the limit between tropical/subtropical moist forests and tropical/subtropical grasslands/savannas/shrublands, the second part of it agreeing with our results. Altogether, a better picture of late Miocene and especially Turolian northwestern environments starts to emerge with mixed environments in a rather subtropical climatic context (MAT being not so high). More northern open landscapes were less widespread than in southern and Southeastern Europe (Barrón et al. 2010; Cihat-Alçiçek et al. 2012) and wooded components, either patchy or most probably interconnected, were largely present. Four flying squirrels are present in Dorn-Dürkheim, two small-sized (*Blackia* and *Pliopetes*), a medium-sized (*Miopetaurista*) and a large-sized (*Pliopetaurista*). Such a taxonomic and size diversity of flying squirrel testifies by itself to the persistence of large interconnected wooded areas. Recent evidence to the South, from the Turolian of Bulgaria, shows a mixed environment with open and wooded areas under a relatively dry and seasonal Mediterranean climate (Clavel et al. 2012). The same environmental characteristics, a “woodland mosaic”, and seasonality would also have prevailed in southeastern Europe (Jiménez-Moreno et al. 2007; Solounias et al. 2010) with warmer winters than at present and aridity controlled by confronting atmospheric conditions over the Atlantic Ocean and

southern Eurasia (Brachert et al. 2006). Dorn-Dürkheim testifies to more humid conditions to the north of the Alps. The presence of water at Dorn-Dürkheim, in the form of a probable river system or water stretches, is well attested by the five beavers and two semi-aquatic adapted desman insectivores (*Desmanella* and *Archaeodesmana*).

Small mammals adapted to open landscapes are less diversified but still well represented at Dorn-Dürkheim, supporting the existence of a mosaic landscape where large wooded areas are interrupted by open vegetation corridors. *Spermophilinus* is a ground squirrel indicating an open component of the environment. As for other microtoid cricetids and later arvicolines (see Fejfar 1999; Fejfar et al. 2011 for a review), the hypsodont and prismatic morphology of *Epimeriones austriacus* molars is interpreted as an adaptation to eating harder plants such as open habitat grasses which are associated with the opening of landscapes all around the world during the late Miocene (Strömberg 2005). Likewise, the appearance of murid rodents, such as *Parapodemus lugdunensis*, at the beginning of the late Miocene in Europe is usually interpreted as a reaction to the general opening of the landscapes (Michaux et al. 1997). Talpinae are also adapted to a fossorial life in rather open environments such as prairies or flood-plains, excluding the possibility of a too dry environment. Based on their parallel evolution with family Spalacidae, anomalomyid rodents such as *Prospalax petteri* might also have been adapted to an underground life (Bolliger 1999), although no preserved post-cranial elements of this extinct family have ever been found to confirm this hypothesis. The environmental complexity is also confirmed by microwear and mesowear analyses of both horses, *H. primigenium* being a mixed feeder incorporating as much as 30 % grass in its diet, while the much rarer *H. kammerschmittae* is a typical browser (Kaiser et al. 2003, 2004). The bovid *Miotragocerus* sp. was found to be intermediate with about 10 % grass in its diet and is supposed to be a closed-areas inhabitant (Gentry and Kaiser 2009).

Conclusions

We analysed the mammalian spectrum of the Dorn-Dürkheim 1 fauna and compared it to the late Miocene European faunal context. Dorn-Dürkheim is one of the richest faunas of the European Miocene with at least 79 species (some still indeterminate, e.g. Chiroptera and Lagomorpha) distributed in at least 29 families and 9 orders. Rodents and carnivores represent more than half of total species diversity which is not exceptional for rich Miocene faunas. In terms of biogeography, Dorn-Dürkheim fits well in the known schemes with its typical Northern European fauna (e.g. even balance Cervidae/Bovidae, presence of several Gliiridae). The fauna contains a mixture of common

and widespread species together with very restricted ones. Several peculiarities are noteworthy: five beavers and five proboscideans are recorded at Dorn-Dürkheim which is a lot in both cases, and unique in the former case. Taxonomic splitting or reworking cannot be totally excluded, but probably not to the point that they could significantly reduce this diversity, implying high habitat diversity. A palaeoenvironmental reconstruction based on body masses and biomasses of the mammalian species confirms the complexity of the landscape. While previous hypotheses regarded Dorn-Dürkheim as a closed forest, our results point to more open conditions. Comparison with present African ecosystems clusters Dorn-Dürkheim's fauna with savanna-woodland biomes which would account for the diversity of large species, and especially megaherbivores. Recent studies (including one in this special issue) of the mesowear of horses and chalicotheres already hint at this result.

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